
Size-dependent direct electrochemical detection of gold nanoparticles: application in magnetoimmunoassays

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5 The effect of the AuNPs size, ranging from 5 nm to 80 nm, on the electrochemical response of screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) used as electrochemical transducers is investigated for the first time. A simple hydrodynamic modelling and calculation at nanoscale level is applied so as to find the effect of the size of AuNP upon the electrochemical response. The results show that the best electrochemical response for AuNP suspension for the same concentration of total gold is obtained for the 20-nm size
10 nanoparticles. It is concluded that the Brownian motions avoid a better response for smaller AuNPs that should in fact be related with the best electrochemical signal due to their higher surface area. Finally, the size effect is studied for AuNPs acting as electroactive labels in an immunosensor that employs magnetic beads as platforms of the bioreactions. The best response for the 5-nm AuNPs in this case is due to the fact that in the immunosensing conditions the Brownian motions are minimized because the AuNPs
15 contact with the electrotransducer surface is induced by the immunoreaction and the fast magnetic collection of the nanoparticles used as antibody labels upon application of a magnetic field.

Introduction

Investigations on nanoparticles (NPs) have rapidly increased in
20 recent years due to their size and shape-dependent physical, chemical and electrochemical properties, which make them extremely useful in sensing and biosensing applications¹. The size and the composition of NPs is advantageous over the corresponding bulk structure because a target binding event, e.g.
25 DNA hybridization or immunoreaction, involving NPs may cause significant effects on their optical (change of light absorption or emission) or electrochemical properties (oxidation or reduction current generated at transducing platform), thereby offering novel options and tools for efficient bioanalysis. In fact, these
30 properties offer signal-transduction modes, including simultaneous approaches (optical and electrochemical)²⁻⁵, that are not available with other materials and systems.

Applications of NPs in biosensing strongly relate to their properties that, in turn, can be tuned through specifically devised
35 synthetic procedures (quality of NPs) and later modifications (chemical and biological). NP-preparation procedures, in colloidal solutions or grown on solid substrates, have been extensively reviewed⁶. Along with advances in synthesis allowing one to control size, shape, and composition of nanostructured
40 materials, our knowledge of how to tailor the NP-binding affinities for various biomolecules through surface modification and engineering has improved significantly. These advancements are now being used to device electrochemical-related applications of NPs in enzyme-based sensors, immunosensors and DNA
45 sensors⁷⁻¹⁰.

In this context, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) stand out from the variety of other nanoparticles and quantum dots because of their

biocompatibility¹¹ and unique electronic, optical, and catalytic properties¹²⁻¹⁶. In particular, AuNPs applications are extensively
50 investigated and tested in immunocytochemistry and cell biology¹⁷. AuNPs have also been used in a variety of analytical^{18,19}, and sensing applications, including DNA^{20,21}, and immuno-sensing²². Although the majority of sensing systems so far described rely on the optical properties of AuNPs, we are
55 currently observing a noticeable growth of AuNP-based immuno²³ and DNA electrochemical assays^{7,8}. The vast majority of these electrochemical approaches is based on chemical dissolution of AuNPs in toxic solutions (i.e. HBr/Br₂) followed by accumulation and stripping analysis of the resulting Au (III)
60 solution. These solutions are highly toxic and therefore alternative approached based on direct electrochemical detection of AuNPs to replace the chemical oxidation agent are sought. In addition to indirect electrocatalytic methods^{24,25}, we^{2,26,27} and others^{4,5} developed a direct detection method based on adsorption
65 of the AuNPs on the surface of the electrotransducer, electrooxidation of the AuNPs to Au (III), and reverse electroreduction to Au (0), which generates a well defined cathodic peak constituting the actual analytical signal. This methodology has been optimized for 20-nm AuNPs on carbon
70 paste and graphite-epoxy electrodes, but the effect of the AuNPs size on the electrochemical signal and the use of other kinds of electrotransducers, such as screen-printed electrodes, has not yet been studied and possibly exploited in biosensors. The size-dependence of the optical properties of AuNPs has been
75 extensively studied, but this effect on the electrochemical properties has not yet been clarified.

Here, we report the size-dependent direct electrochemical detection of AuNPs using screen-printed carbon electrodes

(SPCEs) as electrochemical transducers.

Experimental section

Chemicals and instruments

Gold nanoparticles solutions (supplied diameters: 5, 20, 40, 60, and 80 nm) were purchased from BBInternational (UK). Streptavidin-coated Magnetic Beads (M-280), with 2.8 μm size, were purchased from Dynal Biotech (Invitrogen, Spain). Biotin conjugate-goat anti-human IgG (Sigma B1140, developed in goat and gamma chain specific), human IgG from serum, goat IgG from serum and anti-human IgG (Sigma A8667, developed in goat is whole molecule) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All buffer reagents and other inorganic chemicals were supplied by Sigma, Aldrich or Fluka, unless otherwise stated. All chemicals were used as received and all aqueous solutions were prepared using doubly-distilled water.

The phosphate buffer solution (PBS) consisted of 0.01M phosphate buffered saline, 0.137M NaCl, 0.003M KCl (pH 7.4). Blocking buffer solution consisted of a PBS solution with added 5% (w/v) bovine serum albumin (pH 7.4). The binding and washing (B&W) buffer consisted of a PBS solution containing 0.05% (v/v) Tween 20 (pH 7.4).

A thermostatic centrifugator Sigma 2-16 PK (Fisher Bioblock Scientific, France) was used to purify the conjugates of gold nanoparticles with antibodies.

A semi-automatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK International, Switzerland) was used for the fabrication of the screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), as polyester sheet (McDermid Autotype, UK), Electrodag 423SS carbon ink, Electrodag 6037SS silver/silver chloride ink, and Mimico 7000 Blue insulating ink (Acheson Industries, The Netherlands). Electrochemical measurements were performed at room temperature with an Autolab 20 (Eco-chemie, The Netherlands) connected to a PC.

Spectrophotometric measurements were performed using a Spectramax® M2E multi-mode microplate reader (Molecular Devices Inc, UK).

An Inductively-Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS) model 7500ce (Agilent Technologies, USA) was used to calculate the total gold in the samples.

A Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Jeol JEM-2011 (Jeol Ltd, Japan) was used to characterize the gold nanoparticles. An ultrasonic bath (JP selecta, Spain) was used to prevent agglomeration in the gold nanoparticles solutions before the TEM measurements.

The electrochemical transducers used for the in-situ growth of the cells were homemade screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) consisting of a working electrode, a reference electrode, and a counter electrode inserted on a single strip (for details of the fabrication procedure and images of a SPCE and the 45-sensor sheet, see the *supplementary information*).

AuNPs characterizations

ICP-MS and spectrophotometric analyses were performed to estimate the concentration of AuNPs and total gold contained in each AuNPs solution used for the electrochemical studies. The size and shape of the AuNPs was assessed by transmission electron microscopy. The experimental procedures for these

analyses are detailed in the *supplementary information*.

AuNPs conjugation with antibodies

The conjugation of different size AuNPs (5, 20, and 80 nm of diameter) to anti-human IgG antibodies was performed according to the following procedure, which we previously optimized^{2,24}: 2 mL of a AuNPs suspension, containing 84 μM of total gold, was mixed with 100 μL of 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of the antibody solution and incubated at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min. After that, a blocking step with 150 μL of 1 mg mL^{-1} BSA, incubating at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min was performed. Finally, a centrifugation was carried out in order to purify the conjugate AuNP/anti-human IgG. Centrifugation was performed under different conditions, depending on the size of the AuNPs:

- 5 nm AuNPs: 21000 xg, 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 45 minutes, 2 times.
- 20 nm AuNPs: 14000 xg, 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 10 minutes, 2 times.
- 80 nm AuNPs: 11000 xg, 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2 minutes, 2 times.

Finally, the conjugate AuNPs/anti-human IgG was reconstituted in H_2O milli-Q.

Magnetosandwich immunoassay using as labels AuNPs of different sizes

The preparation of the magnetic beads (MBs) based sandwich type immunocomplex was performed following a method that we previously optimized^{2,24}. MBs modified with streptavidin were used to immobilize specific antibodies against human IgG. After the capture of the human IgG in the sample, the sandwich was formed with secondary specific antibodies conjugated with AuNPs. A blank (control) assay was performed using goat IgG instead of human IgG at the same concentration. The experimental procedure is detailed in the *supplementary information*.

Electrochemical analysis

The electrochemical analysis of AuNPs was performed by placing 25 μL of the AuNPs solution on the working electrode area of the SPCEs and leaving the AuNPs to adsorb during 2 minutes. After that, 25 μL of a HCl 0.2 M solution were added, covering the three electrodes area. The pre-concentration step, meant to oxidize AuNPs to AuCl_4^- , was performed at +1.25 V (vs Ag/AgCl) for 120s in a quiescent solution. Immediately after the electrochemical oxidation, differential pulse voltammetry was performed by scanning from +1.25 V to 0.0 V (step potential 10 mV, modulation amplitude 50 mV, scan rate 33.5 mV s^{-1}), resulting in the analytical signal caused by reduction of AuCl_4^- at +0.45 V.

For the magnetosandwich-immunoassay measurements, we applied the same protocol, but for placing a MBs solution instead of a AuNPs solution on the SPCE. A magnet was placed on the opposite side of the strip relative to the working electrode.

Results and discussion

Direct electrochemical detection of gold nanoparticles

The size and shape of the AuNPs were first determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis. Figure 1A

shows the TEM images obtained for most of the AuNPs studied, together with the corresponding sizes distribution. As can be observed, Gaussian distributions were obtained, being the main values (and their deviations) of 6.5 (+/- 1.1), 8.5 (+/- 1.7), 17.5 (+/- 2.0), 38.3 (+/- 4.5), 54.9 (+/- 6.1) and 73.9 (+/- 8.9) nm for the “5”, “10”, “20”, “40”, “60” and “80” nm supplied values respectively. However, in order to facilitate the understanding of the results, the values given by the NPs supplier only are mentioned along the text.

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy of the AuNPs solutions, in the 528–540 nm range where the gold plasmon resonance band appears²⁸, evidenced absence of aggregation. As expected, the wavelength of the maximum of absorbance undergoes a red shift as the AuNPs size increases. An estimation of the concentration of AuNPs was obtained by measuring the optical density at 450 nm and knowing the molar decadic extinction coefficient (ϵ) at this wavelength, which has been previously calculated for each AuNP size by Haiss²⁹ (see the calculations in the *supplementary information*).

A key step of our procedure for the electrochemical detection of AuNPs consists in an efficient adsorption of AuNPs onto the surface of the electrotransducer, which will allow their further oxidation and then reduction of the ensuing oxidized gold species. The efficient adsorption of 20-nm AuNPs onto the surface of the SPCEs, according to the experimental procedure detailed in experimental section, seems to be evidenced in the SEM images shown in figure 1B, where in spite of the rugosity of the carbon surface it seems that the AuNPs are adsorbed and spread onto the carbon surface without agglomerates formation; this is important for allowing a reproducible electrochemical detection in the further steps.

We previously reported results about the direct electrochemical detection of AuNPs on graphite-epoxy composite electrodes^{2,26,27}. We are now reporting data concerning further important issues. One aspect we addressed was to study the electrochemical features of this AuNP-based approach by using SPCEs, which provide an advantageous platform in terms of miniaturization, low volume of samples, single use possibilities, and convenient mass-production related technology. In addition to the use of a novel transducing surface, main objective of this work was to study the effect of the AuNP size on the electrochemical signal. In particular, we anticipated that this issue would have had important effects on both the sensitivity and the reproducibility of the affinity bioassays (i.e. DNA sensors or immunosensor) requiring the use of labels.

Figure 2A shows cartoons of the detection steps pertaining to AuNPs with three different sizes (small, medium, large); AuNP suspensions consist of the same number of AuNPs. After the AuNPs are deposited onto the SPE surface from the appropriate suspension (step 1), their partial electrochemical oxidation (step 2), generating a high surface concentration of Au(III) ions by the

Figure 1. (A) TEM images obtained for 5-nm (a), 20-nm (b), 40-nm (c) and 80-nm (d) AuNPs solutions and the corresponding sizes distribution. (B) SEM images of the SPCE electrotransducer (a) and the 20-nm AuNPs deposited on the carbon working area from a solution of 1×10^{10} AuNPs mL^{-1} , following the experimental procedure detailed in experimental section at 100.000 X amplifications (b).

electrotransducer, occurs. Anodic stripping of the adsorbed AuNPs is then followed by a potential scan to reductive potentials (step 3): the peak current for reduction of Au(III) ions to Au(0) is related to the original surface concentration of the AuNPs.

For the same number of nanoparticles, AuNPs of different sizes were also expected to provoke different behaviors in terms of reduction peak potentials for Au(0) deposition. The value of the peak current was expected to be higher for larger AuNPs (for the same number of nanoparticles) due to their higher surface area generating a higher surface concentration of released gold ions during the oxidation step. As depicted in the cartoon of step 3, deposition of gold occurs onto smaller, residual AuNPs, as during the stripping step AuNPs are partially oxidized (being their size slightly reduced). Due to an ‘incomplete stripping’³⁰, the remaining AuNPs, of different area, act as an array of nanoelectrodes that catalyze the further electrodeposition, that consequently should occur at different potentials in comparison to the bare carbon electrode.

On the other hand, it is conceivable that if one starts from the same total gold ion concentration (see figure 2B), smaller AuNPs would result in the detection of larger peak currents, as small NPs are present in a larger number, provide a higher quantity of surface atoms (the ratio between the surface and the core gold atoms increases as the NP is made smaller), and increase the area of contacting surface between them and the electrotransducing surface. Furthermore, the reduction potential of the gold ions should be shifted to less negative potentials, due to a better array-like effect for smaller compared to larger sizes NPs.

To verify our expectations, we carried out experiments focusing on two sets of conditions for the AuNP suspensions. In the first set we used AuNP suspensions with varying core sizes but with the same number of nanoparticles. In the second set we kept the total amount of gold constant: because of the different core sizes, this procedure resulted in AuNP suspensions containing a different number of nanoparticles.

Figure 2. (A). Schematic, not in scale, of the three steps used for introduction and detection of small (s), medium (m) and large (l) size AuNP suspension of the same number of AuNPs using a SPCE. Step 1 corresponds to AuNP deposition onto SPE surface. Step 2 corresponds to gold ion release/oxidation upon the application of a +1.25 V potential during 120s. Step 3 corresponds to gold ion deposition /reduction onto the SPE by scanning from +1.25 V to 0.0 V. (B). Schematic of the third step only in the case when the total gold concentration is the same.

Size-effect on the voltammetric response for the same number of gold nanoparticles

As a first step, the effect of the AuNPs size on the electrochemical signal for the same concentration of AuNPs, previously determined by UV-Vis spectrophotometry, was evaluated. As it is detailed in experimental section, an oxidation potential of +1.25 V was applied to the adsorbed AuNPs in order to release the Au (III) ions (step 2, Figure 2A). In the case of gold, the standard state in the pure crystalline bulk metal, and the generation of Au (III) ions from the AuNPs in a hydrochloric medium is given by³¹:

For convenience, the shape of AuNPs is taken as that of a perfect sphere and, accordingly, the volumes of single 5-, 20- and 80-nm-diameter particles are calculated to be 5.23×10^{-19} , 2.09×10^{-18} and $8.36 \times 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^3$, respectively. By taking the density of the AuNP to be that of bulk gold (ρ), 19.3 g cm^{-3} the atomic mass (M) to be $196.967 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, and Avogadro's number (N_A) to be 6.022×10^{23} , the approximate numbers of atoms per particle (N) are 3859, 246960 and 15806976, respectively, according with the following equation^{32,33}:

$$N = \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho D^3 N_A / 6M \quad (2)$$

where D is the diameter of the NP.

These values are much greater than the more than 100 atoms needed to start producing "bulk character"³⁴ and, as such, to have the same standard potential, E° , of gold, as this value is quoted for all species in their standard states. The range of particle sizes considered in this work, in a similar mode as for Compton's silver nanoparticles³⁵ is narrow, and therefore, it is assumed that the value of this standard potential is the same for the different-sized AuNPs studied. It means that the potential of +1.25 V applied is oxidative enough to oxidize the surface of the AuNPs and to generate Au (III) ions.

After the oxidation step, we applied a negative-going differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) scan to the SPCE and obtained voltammograms such as those shown in figure 3A. The results show that gold ion reduction onto larger AuNPs occurs at less negative potentials ($\sim 60 \text{ mV}$ shift) than observed for smaller size particles, due to an increased nanoarray like effect (figure 2A, step 3). Regarding the peak current, directly related to the

Figure 3. (A) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained for AuNPs of different diameters in solutions containing $1 \times 10^{10} \text{ AuNPs mL}^{-1}$. (a) 5 nm, (b) 10 nm, (c) 20 nm, (d) 40 nm, (e) 60 nm, (f) 80 nm. Step potential: 10mV, modulation amplitude: 50mV, scan rate 33.5 mV s^{-1} (non-stirred solution). (B) AuNPs size dependence on the analytical signal for different AuNPs concentrations: (a) 1×10^{11} , (b) 1×10^{10} , (c) $1 \times 10^9 \text{ AuNPs mL}^{-1}$.

quantity of gold ions and indirectly to the AuNP quantity, figure 3A shows that the maximum analytical signals, obtained by following the experimental procedure described in experimental section, were obtained for the largest NP employed, i.e., the 80-nm AuNPs. The same behavior was observed for different AuNP concentrations, as shown in the plots of figure 3B (full data are provided in the *supplementary information*). As for the peak potential, the increase of the DPV peaks as the AuNP size also increases are in agreement with the expected behavior, because for the same number of NPs the number of released gold ions (and, consequently, of those available for the following reduction step) can be related with the number of surface atoms in the AuNPs, which in turn is related to the size of the AuNPs (Figure 2A, step 2).

Size-effect on the voltammetric response for the same concentration of total gold

The effect of the AuNPs size onto the electrochemical response for the same concentration of total gold, previously determined by inductively-coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), was also studied. We expected (Figure 2B) that for the same quantity of total gold, smaller AuNPs would have yielded a higher electrochemical signal, as for smaller AuNPs a higher surface area, implying a higher number of surface atoms (see a summary table in the *supplementary information*), is in contact with the working electrode surface. Consequently, a higher number of Au (III) ions would be released from the bulk metal due to the electrochemical oxidation step, giving rise to a higher voltammetric peak recorded during the ions reduction step. The DPVs obtained for different AuNPs at a total gold concentration of $200 \mu\text{M}$ are shown in figure 4A. The predicted behavior is indeed observed in the range 20-80 nm (c,d,e voltammograms). In these experiments, a positive shift of the reduction potential ($\sim 30 \text{ mV}$) was observed for the smaller AuNPs. This can be attributed again to array effect of the remaining AuNPs and its promoting role on the reduction of Au(III) ions to Au(0). As also predicted, the peak current is smaller for larger AuNPs. However, for AuNPs in the range from 5 to 20 nm (voltammograms a, b, and c: voltammogram c, corresponding to the 20 nm AuNP, is included for comparison purposes) we found the opposite effects in terms of both reduction potential and peak current intensity. The shift of the reduction potential ($\sim 80 \text{ mV}$) is even more pronounced. This general trend was consistently observed for

Figure 4. (A) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained for AuNPs of different sizes – (a) 5 nm, (b) 10 nm, (c) 20 nm, (d) 60 nm, (e) 80 nm - containing a concentration of total gold of 200 μM . DPV parameters as in figure 3A. (B) AuNPs size dependence on the analytical signal for different total gold concentrations: (a) 10 μM , (b) 20 μM , (c) 50 μM , (d) 200 μM . (C) Scheme of the process occurring on the electrode surface for the different AuNPs sizes. V_s stands for “setting velocity” as detailed in experimental section.

different total gold concentrations tested, as shown in the plots of figure 4B.

An explanation to these contradictory results may be related to the Brownian effects³⁶ governing the motion of these smaller particles. Any minute particle suspended in a liquid (or gas) moves chaotically under the action of collisions with surrounding molecules. The frictional force -also called drag force- exerted on spherical objects with very small Reynolds numbers (e.g., nanoparticles) in a continuous viscous fluid can be calculated by the Stokes Law³⁷: if the particles are falling in a viscous fluid by their own weight due to gravity, then a terminal velocity, also known as the settling velocity, is reached when this frictional force combined with the buoyant force exactly balance the gravitational force. From equations derived from this law, the settling velocity of the AuNPs of different sizes from the suspension to the electrode surface and the necessary falling time to the electrode surface from an arbitrary distance can be estimated. These approximated calculations are detailed in the *supplementary information*, showing that for the 5-nm AuNPs, the expected time of AuNPs deposition of those situated at a distance of, say, 50 nm (an arbitrary distance chosen as long enough to put in evidence the different behaviors between the smaller and the larger AuNPs in relatively short, i.e. 2 minutes, adsorption time) over the electrotransducer surface would be 32 minutes. This means that, after drop casting the AuNPs suspension onto the electrode surface, a deposition time of 2 minutes (used in the detection procedure) is not long enough to guarantee quantitative adsorption of AuNPs smaller than 20 nm onto the electrode surface. If part (or even most) of the AuNPs are still not adsorbed onto the electrotransducer surface, the electrochemical signal coming from the AuNPs will dramatically decrease. On the other hand, the AuNPs of 20-80 nm situated at the same 50 nm distance from the electrode surface will be totally adsorbed within the 2 minutes deposition time. A cartoon of the process hypothesized to occur on the electrode surface is shown

Figure 5. (A) (Left) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained for magnetosandwich immunoassays performed using AuNPs labels of different sizes: (b) 80 nm, (c) 20 nm and (d) 5 nm. (a) curve corresponds to a blank immunoassay carried out with goat IgG instead of human IgG and AuNPs labels of 5 nm. (Right) Corresponding AuNPs labels size dependence on the analytical signals obtained for the magnetosandwich immunoassay using as electrochemical labels AuNPs of different sizes prepared from solutions of 84 μM of total gold as detailed in experimental section. Experimental procedure also detailed in experimental section. DPV parameters as in figure 3A. (B) Scheme of the process on the electrode surface – where a magnet has been placed under the working electrode area- for only AuNPs (left) and for the AuNPs attached to magnetic beads through the immunoassay (right).

in figure 4C.

Overall, the results obtained under the same experimental protocol indicate that, for the same quantity of total gold, efficiency is optimized with the 20-nm AuNPs. In other words, for the same quantity of gold the best way to exploit the electrochemical properties of AuNPs is to use the 20-nm sized ones. Smaller AuNPs suffer the problem of the longer times required to be adsorbed onto the electrode surface due to Brownian effects.

Application in a magnetoimmunoassay

We also studied the effect of the AuNPs size on the electrochemical signal when the NPs are used as labels in an immunoassay system based on the use of magnetic particles (MB) as immobilization platform. Under these conditions, we expected that the Brownian effects would have been minimized because independently of their size all AuNPs would be attracted onto the electrotransducer surface upon application of the magnetic field.

To study the effect of size, AuNPs of different sizes were conjugated with antibodies (see experimental section) and used as labels in a magnetosandwich immunoassay that we previously optimized for 20-nm AuNPs^{2,24}, using magnetic beads (MB) as platforms of the immunoreactions (see experimental section). Briefly, it consists in the immobilization of biotin-modified anti-human IgG antibodies onto the surface of streptavidin-coated magnetic beads followed by the human IgG capturing from the sample. Finally the sandwich is completed through the immunoreaction with anti-human IgG-AuNP secondary antibodies. (MB/anti-human IgG/Human IgG / anti-human IgG-AuNP). It is well known that magneto-based immunoassays

present improved properties in terms of sensitivity and selectivity, due to the preconcentration of the analyte, the separation from the matrix of the sample and the immobilization / collection on the transducer surface, achieved using a magnetic field. Figure 5A shows the electrochemical signals obtained for the same total concentration of gold with different AuNPs sizes (5, 20, and 80 nm) used as labels in the described magnetoimmunoassay. The DPV peak-current values show that a higher peak current was obtained for the 5-nm AuNPs. In addition, the peak potential was found to shift to less negative potentials as the AuNP size decreased. These results confirm that the Brownian effects are not relevant when the AuNPs are attached to the MBs through the immunoreaction (as schematized in figure 5B) being these attracted afterward by a magnet placed under the working electrode surface. Therefore, under magnetosandwich conditions, the higher surface area of the smaller AuNPs gives rise to the best electrochemical response.

Conclusions

The electrochemical properties of gold nanoparticles suspensions are strongly depended on the size and the hydrodynamic properties of the solvent. By considering only the NPs' size and for a fixed quantity of gold, smaller size NPs generate higher DPV signals. On the other hand, owing to the solvent effect and while working at a constant electrochemical measuring time, larger NPs generate higher signals. Our analysis points to Brownian effects as the main factor governing the efficiency of smaller size NPs. Conversely, while working in a bioassay system such as magnetoimmunoassay employing magnetic particles, the mentioned effect is suppressed due to the fact that the NPs labels are attracted to the electrotransducer surface upon application of a magnetic field as witnessed by the increase of the DPV signal for the smallest NPs.

However we consider that the Brownian effect should be carefully considered according to the experimental conditions. For example, in an integrated biosensing system where the antibodies (or DNA capture probes) are directly immobilized onto the transducing surface the approaching of NPs upon the recognition event would highly depend on the size. This consideration should be crucial for microfluidics based biosensing systems (i.e. lab-on-a-chip) designs employing NPs based labeling technology. The design of optical based biosystems also might take advantages of such an approximation that would enlarge the importance of such a phenomena.

These results are considered to provide an important piece of information to obtain a better understanding of the properties of gold nanoparticles and, more generally, for the optimization of AuNPs-based electrochemical bioassays relevant not only to proteins but also to DNA and cells sensing.

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Notes and references

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- ⁶⁰ † Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: detailed experimental procedures and related figures, calculations for the estimation of the settling velocity and deposition time for AuNPs of different sizes and tables summarizing these and other calculations. See DOI: 10.1039/b000000x/
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